

Fostering Improved Training Tools For Responsible Research and Innovation FIT4RRI

Data Management Plan (Deliverable 7.12)

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Summary

Abstract	2
1 Objective of Data Management Plan (DMP)	4
2 Data Set	5
3 Standards and metadata	6
4 Data Sharing	6
5 Data Repository	8

Abstract

The Deliverable 7.2 deals with the drafting of FIT4RRI data management plan (DMP) and aims at

describing the main obligations and responsibilities that all Consortium Members have in terms of data standards and their storage and protection, during the project and beyond its completion. It includes a classification of data potentially produced by Consortium Members and presents the open access solution opted out for RES URBIS peer-reviewed scientific publications.

The DMP also deals with those cases implying that all or parts of the project research data cannot be openly shared on account of copyright issues, confidentiality or personal data protection requirements or when open dissemination could jeopardize the project achievements.

As a result, the plan is divided into the following sections:

- DMP objectives
- Data set
- Standards and metadata
- Data sharing
- Data repository.

1 Objective of Data Management Plan (DMP)

This DMP provides a guideline regarding how to manage the research data collected and generated within the FIT4RRI Project (Grant n. 741477).

More in details, this plan describes the main obligations and responsibilities that all Consortium Members have in terms of data standards and their storage and protection, during the project and beyond its completion. The DMP also deals with those cases implying that all or parts of the project research data cannot be openly shared on account of copyright issues, confidentiality or personal data protection requirements or when open dissemination could jeopardize the project achievements.

The present document takes into consideration the “Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020”¹ (version 3.1 issued in August 2016) as well as “Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020”² (version 3.0 issued in July 2016)

Due to its nature of “developing” document, the DMP will be adapted to any change the project may undergo and any new version to be issued, if needed, will undergo to electronic remote voting for its approval. In particular the present version has been peer-reviewed and will be presented at the next General Assembly which is foreseen in Trondheim on November 9-10. Any future amendment will have to be approved by the FIT4RRI General Assembly (including by using electronic vote).

FIT4RRI project Consortium in defining what can be shared openly and what could raise intellectual property will get support from the following scheme proposed by EU IPR Helpdesk as well as from the documents produced by the Helpesk itself.

Subject Matter	Patent	Utility Model	Industrial Design	Copyright	Trade Mark	Confidential Information
Invention (e.g. device, process, method¹)	X	X				X
Software	X ²	X		X		X
Scientific article				X		
Design of a product			X	X	X	
Name of a technology/product					X	
Know How	X	X				X
Website			X	X	X	X

Fig. 1 – Protection instruments by subject matters

Source: *European IPR Helpdes*

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf

² http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf

2 Data Set

All data produced will be classified in an intuitive way to favour their recognisability and will be constantly update to keep trace of all revisions occurred by a proper naming (es. Rev X.Y).

In particular, FIT4RRI project has chosen a classification method based on type of content according to the following categories:

- technical (operational or scientific)
- business and marketing
- general dissemination.

As a result, we could imagine the dataset and data types description as presented in table 1:

Data	Description	Type	Stakeholders	Dissemination level
Scientific/Technical Reports Deliverables	Description of results, mostly through Deliverables	Technical Scientific	Consortium	Confidential or Public
Scientific publications	Articles for academic journals	Scientific	Scientific Community	Open Access (Gold or green rule)
Presentation to Scientific Conferences	Oral or Poster presentations	Scientific	Scientific Community	Public to the attendance
Business strategy/Exploitation plan/	Documents and presentations	Business	Consortium Selected Stakeholders	Confidential
Marketing presentations	Communication presentations describing project's business strategy	Business - Marketing	SMEs, Investors, Researchers	Open Access/Public
Press releases	Releases for mainstream communication through newspapers, websites and magazines	General dissemination	Large public	Public/Open Access
Social media	Releases for mainstream communication social media (FeceBook, Twetter, LinkedIn,..)	General dissemination	Large public	Public/Open Access
Web site/contents	All contents presented in	General dissemination	Large public	Public/Open Access

	FIT4RRI websites to promote and describe the project			
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3 Standards and metadata

FIT4RRI DMP aims at ensuring standard procedures to define and classify data according to the following principles:

1. Each beneficiary will produce data according to its tasks within relevant project activities;
2. Methodology for data management and protection could differ according to the type of activities and content produced, but it will always follow the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement principles;
3. A project repository accessible for Consortium Members through FIT4RRI Emdesk page has been implemented to store data, reports and documents;
4. Unless differently agreed at the next General Assembly, all beneficiaries will use ZENODO³ repository for open access data.

Data will be stored in FIT4RRI internal repository according to the classification presented in Table 1 and by following the project's structure (WPs, tasks, deliverables). Particular attention will be dedicated to versioning, that will be underlined through a progressive number such as rev x.y, the date of release, and the delivering Party short name in each document.

Interim versions of deliverables and reports and any other interim document will be hosted in a dedicated folder where each Party has access right both to download previous version and to upload its own revised version. Validated document will be hosted in a dedicated folder.

Data file will include a short and self-explaining description of the relevant content, author (FIT4RRI beneficiaries short name) and revision.

Metadata will be used to record all data generating all Figures and Table and will be attached to the data set itself as a separate table with an adequate legenda of the data meaning and in an editable way, for data's future use. Any additional metadata will be added whenever needed or useful on judgement of the releasing Party or upon reasoned request of another Party or the PC whenever useful to fulfill following Tasks.

4 Data Sharing

Data and knowledge sharing under H2020 is described in several guidelines as well as in the Grant Agreement and in the Consortium Agreement.

More in detail, article 29.2 of the GA sets out detailed legal requirements on open access to scientific publications that, under Horizon 2020, must be ensured to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. To this regard, all FIT4RRI beneficiaries will guarantee open access to their scientific publications in terms of online reading, downloading and printing through both Gold open access and Green open access.

More in detail, a specific budget needed to support Gold Open access has been already allocated by all Parties doing scientific research and will be used for that purpose accordingly (as specified in

³ www.zenodo.org

Table 3.4.2 of the DoA). For additional scientific publications overcoming the allocated budget, the Parties will be free to use the Green open access.

Given the budget limitations, Gold Open Access will be preferentially used for publications with very high level of novelty and/or underlying multidisciplinary cooperation among Parties.

In order to comply with Open Access policy, recently the PC UNIROMA1 has integrated into its research products repository IRIS⁴ a tool for open access publications provided by OpenAIRE project⁵. Currently only metadata for open access are available, but UNIROMA1 is working on a validation system to allow the full text OA publication.

Dealing with Consortium Agreements requirements, it is relevant to underline that FIT4RRI CA foresees:

- under Section 8 the ownership, joint ownership, dissemination and transfer of FIT4RRI results according to the EC principles;
- under Section 9 the access rights both in terms of background and foreground;
- under section 10 non-disclosure of information and confidentiality of data and info among Consortium Members.

More in detail, as established in the CA , section 8.4.2.1. prior notice of any planned publication, including copy of the planned publication or a detailed summary, shall be given to the other Parties at least 30 calendar days before the intended date of publication or 15 calendar days before a poster presentation or an oral disclosure. Any objection to the planned publication or communication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement in writing to the Coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within 21 calendar days after receipt of the notice in case of publication and 10 days in case of oral communication or poster. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication or communication is permitted. Moreover, as prescribed under art. 29.4 of the GA, dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) will

(a) display the EU emblem and

(b) include the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 730349” .

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem will have appropriate prominence.

Regarding FIT4RRI results, the Consortium will pay particular attention to the deployment of the research results value chain (see figure below) and will carefully decide which data and documents will be public and which ones will be confidential.

⁴ <https://iris.uniroma1.it/>

⁵ <https://www.openaire.eu/>

Fig. 2 – Research Value Chain *Source: European IPR Helpdesk*

5 Data Repository

As already mentioned, ZENODO is considered the best choice as data repository for the following reasons:

- It is multidisciplinary, collaborative and international
- It supports all kind of formats and published documents
- It supports open, embargoed, restricted and closed data (<https://zenodo.org/policies>)
- It allows files submission up to 2 GB (with specific arrangements for largel files), if needed PC could pay for size upgrading
- It allows a variety of licenses although the open licenses are recommended, with description under Creative Commons License (<http://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>)
- It identifies research data and products through Digital Object Identifier (DOI)
- It was developed by CERN within OpenAIRE project and it is therefore recommended for EU projects
- It preserves and sores data at the CERN Data Center
- It integrates, if needed, ORCID, GitHub and DropBox
- It allows to export citations to bibliographic managers and social networks
- It allows to add link to related documents

Dealing finally with the preservation and storage of confidential data, they will be under related beneficiary and Task Leader (supervised by WorkPackage Leader) responsibility, who will have the duty of ensuring back-ups of the data and will be obliged to make data available to other beneficiaries upon request for five years after project completion.

